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ÖN SÖZ

18. Uluslararası Dil, Edebiyat ve Kültür Araştırmaları Kongresi, 08-11 Ekim 2024 tarihlerinde Ankara'da gerçekleşti. Bu kongre, Saybider Topluluğunun organizasyonunda ve başta Ankara Hacı Bayram Veli Üniversitesi, Mardin Artuklu Üniversitesi, Carthage University olmak üzere çeşitli yükseköğretim kurumlarının ilmi desteği ile düzenlenmektedir. Kongreye 6 farklı ülkeden davetli konuşmacı davet edilmiştir. Aynı zamanda Türkçe, İngilizce ve Arapça duyurular yapılarak bilim insanlarına çağrıda bulunulmuştur. Bu çağrılar sonrasında Türkiye hariç 13 farklı ülkeden (Birleşik Krallık, Cezayir, Çin, Endonezya, Fas, Filistin, Irak, İran, Mısır, Suriye, Suudi Arabistan Krallığı, Umman, Ürdün) sözlü bildiri kongre programına dâhil edilmiştir. Tüm bildiriler kör hakemlik sürecinden geçirildikten sonra sunuma kabul veya reddi gerçekleştirilmiştir. Bu süreç içerisinde bildirilerin önemli bir kısmına hakemlerden düzeltme talebi gelmiştir. Hakemler tarafından talep edilen düzeltmelerin yapılıp yapılmadığı da özenle kontrol edilmiş ve düzeltilerden sonra kabul mektupları düzenlenerek yazarlarına gönderilmiştir.

Başvuru süreci sonucunda 72'i Türk bilim insanları tarafından ve 80'i farklı ülkelerden katılan bilim insanları tarafından hazırlanmış toplam 152 bildiri sözlü sunuma uygun bulunmuştur. Bu kitapta bilim insanlarının kongrede sunduğu bildirilerin tam metinlerine yer verilmiştir. Bu sunumların geniş kitlelere ulaşarak alana faydalı olmasını ve yeni çalışmalara ilham vermesini diliyorum.

Kongrenin bilim insanları arasındaki iletişimi kuvvetlendirmesini, bilgi alışverişini arttırmasını, ortak çalışma zeminlerini oluşturmasını, milletimize, insanlığa ve bilgiyle amel edenlere faydalı olmasını diliyorum.

Prof. Dr. Yakup Civelek
Düzenleme Kurulu Başkanı

مقدمة

يأتي هذا الكتاب نتيجًا لجهود مجموعة من الباحثين البارزين الذين شاركوا بأبحاثهم في المؤتمر الدولي الثامن عشر للغات والآداب والدراسات الثقافية، والذي عُقد في أنقرة خلال الفترة من 8 إلى 11 أكتوبر. يعد هذا المؤتمر أحد أبرز الفعاليات الأكاديمية التي تجمع بين مختلف التخصصات في مجال العلوم الإنسانية، حيث شارك فيه باحثون من أكثر من عشرين دولة من مختلف القارات، مما أضفى طابعًا عالميًا ومتنوعًا على المناقشات التي جرت.

تميز المؤتمر بالتنوع الثقافي واللغوي الذي انعكس في الأوراق البحثية المقدمة، حيث تناول الباحثون قضايا متعددة تشمل الأدب الكلاسيكي والمعاصر، اللغات الحديثة والقديمة، ودراسات الثقافة وتأثيراتها على المجتمعات المختلفة. ولم يقتصر النقاش على دراسة الأعمال الأدبية أو تحليل النصوص اللغوية فحسب، بل تطرق إلى استكشاف العلاقة بين اللغة والثقافة وكيف تساهم في تشكيل الهويات الفردية والجماعية.

تمحورت العديد من الأبحاث حول قضايا مثل تأثير العولمة على اللغات والثقافات المحلية، وكيفية المحافظة على التراث الثقافي واللغوي في مواجهة التغيرات المتسارعة. كما سلطت الأبحاث الضوء على دور الأدب في نقل التجارب الإنسانية والتعبير عن القضايا الاجتماعية والسياسية، ما أضاف أبعادًا جديدة لفهمنا للأدب كوسيلة للتغيير الاجتماعي والثقافي. في هذا السياق، عُرضت دراسات معمقة حول الترجمة ودورها في بناء جسور بين الثقافات المختلفة، حيث كانت الترجمة موضوعًا محوريًا في العديد من الأبحاث التي ناقشت التحديات التي تواجه المترجمين في نقل النصوص بما يحافظ على أصالتها وسياقها الثقافي. وقد أضافت هذه الأبحاث أبعادًا جديدة للفهم العالمي للأدب واللغة كوسائل لتبادل الأفكار والتجارب بين الشعوب.

من الجدير بالذكر أن المؤتمر تناول أيضًا التحولات التي تشهدها اللغات والأدب في العصر الرقمي، حيث تم تسليط الضوء على تأثير التكنولوجيا الحديثة على كيفية إنتاج النصوص الأدبية وتلقيها. وقدمت أبحاث حول كيفية توظيف الأدوات الرقمية في تحليل النصوص الأدبية، مما أتاح فرصًا جديدة للتفاعل مع الأدب بطرق مبتكرة ومختلفة.

هذا الكتاب يضم بين صفحاته نتائج عمل أكاديمي متميز يُظهر مدى التنوع والغنى الفكري الذي تمتعت به فعاليات هذا المؤتمر. فالأوراق البحثية المنشورة هنا ليست مجرد عرض لقضايا أدبية أو لغوية، بل هي محاولات جادة لاستكشاف العلاقات العميقة بين النصوص، الثقافات، والمجتمعات، وكيف يمكن أن يساهم فهم هذه العلاقات في تعزيز التواصل بين الشعوب في زمن يشهد فيه العالم تحديات متزايدة تتعلق بالتنوع الثقافي واللغوي.

نأمل أن يجد القارئ في هذا الكتاب إضافة غنية للنقاشات العلمية حول اللغات والآداب والدراسات الثقافية، وأن يكون محفزًا لمزيد من البحوث التي تسعى لفهم أعمق لتلك التخصصات الإنسانية التي تعد جزءًا أساسيًا من تشكيل هوياتنا وفهمنا للعالم. وختامًا، نود أن نعبر عن شكرنا لكل الباحثين الذين أسهموا بأبحاثهم في هذا المؤتمر، وكذلك لجميع الجهات المنظمة والداعمة التي ساهمت في إنجاح هذا الحدث الأكاديمي المتميز.

İçindekiler - فهرس - Contents

Kutadgu Bilig’de Kalem ve Kılıç	377
Doç. Dr. Salih Demirbilek	
Türk Müziği Solfej Eğitiminde Deşifre Becerilerini Geliştirmek İçin Bir Öneri: Dört Adım Yaklaşımı	386
Dr. Öğr. Üyesi Çağlar Toptaş	
Arap Alfabesinde Harflerin Dizilişi ve Alfabe Öğretimine İlişkin Bazı Sorunlar	396
Doç. Dr. Nazife Nihal İnce	
Bitki ve Hayvan Örnekleme Bağlamında “Kitâb-ı Atalar Sözi”ndeki Sembolizm Üzerine Bir Değerlendirme	405
Dr. Öğr. Üyesi Muhammed Avşar	
Siyâveş-İ Kısrayî’ nin <i>Gazel Berayî Direht</i> (Ağaca Gazel) Şiirine Bir Bakış.....	436
Arş. Gör. Dr. Dilek Sakaroğlu	
444	محاكاة المقامة الحديثة للمقامة التراثية - المقامة الحلبية لليازجي نموذجاً
Dr. Öğr. Üyesi Nadir Menderes	
<i>Göçmen Bavulu</i> Metaforu Üzerinden Gerçekleştirilen Sanatsal İfadeler	457
Dr. Evrim Kabukcu	

- Göçün Feminizasyonu: *Kadınların Göç Hafızası Örneği*..... 467
Dr. Evrim Kabukcu
- Religious Fanaticism and Colonial Vulnerability in Marlon James's *John Crow's Devil: An Exploration of Internal Conflict and External Domination*..... 476
Doç. Dr. Mehmet Recep Taş
19. Yüzyıl Âşık Şiirinde Ferhat ile Şirin Hikâyesi Bağlamında İntihar Temi..... 489
Prof. Dr. Kadriye Türkan
- Dijital Kültür Bağlamında 21. Yüzyıl Âşıklarına Ait Facebook Cönkleri..... 497
Prof. Dr. Kadriye Türkan
Yüksek Lisans Öğrencisi Şeyma Mert
- Semîn El-Halebî'nin Ed-Dürrü'l-Masûn Fî 'Ulûmi'l-Kitâbi'l-Meknûn İsimli Eserinde Züheyr B. Ebi Sülmâ'nın Muallakasından Yapılan İstîşadlar Üzerine Bir İnceleme..... 509
Yüksek Lisans Öğrencisi Ayşe Sena Ünlü
Doç. Dr. Bünyamin Aydın
- Yabancılara Türkçe Öğretiminde İsimlerde Tümleme Yapılarının Edinimi..... 523
Lisansüstü Öğrencisi Kübra Bahar
- Palestinian Narratives of Displacement and Resistance: A Postcolonial Reading..... 539
Dr. Taghreed Gamal Elbakly

558.....التواصل اللغوي بين العربية والفارسية مظاهر تأثير العربية في الفارسية نموذجاً

عبد الكريم جرادات

The Interplay of Power and Corruption in Hanya Yanagihara's *The People in the Trees* through a Foucauldian Lens 572

Doç. Dr. Mehmet Recep Taş

Tara June Winch'in *The Yield* Romanında Kültürel Asimilasyon Bağlamında Dilin ve Kültürel Mirasın Korunması..... 581

Doç. Dr. Mehmet Recep Taş

Tuva Türkçesinde Sözlüksel Ettirgenlik İşaretleyicilerinin Kullanımı 588

Dr. Öğr. Üyesi Tuğba Sarıkaya Aksoy

Türkçede Yaygın Olarak Kullanılan Arapça Kelimelerin Yapısı ve Sistematiği 596

Dr. Öğr. Üyesi Yakup Eroğlu

Kırık Hayatlar Romanında Güzel ve Yüce Üzerine..... 614

Arş. Gör. Dr. Zeynep Şener

630.....البنية الصرفية للمشتقات في الشعر الصوفي وأثرها في توجيه المعنى الرواس نموذجاً

Dr. Öğr. Üyesi M. Salem Assad

638.....التواصل اللغوي بين العربية والفارسية: مظاهر تأثير العربية في الفارسية نموذجاً

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Abstract

This paper examines the interplay of power and corruption in Hanya Yanagihara's novel *The People in the Trees* through a Foucauldian lens. Drawing on Michel Foucault's concept of power, the analysis delves into the complex dynamics between knowledge, authority, and ethical boundaries as depicted in the narrative. The protagonist, Dr. Norton Perina, embodies the dual roles of a celebrated scientist and a morally compromised individual, reflecting Foucault's assertion that power is both productive and repressive. By exploring Perina's interactions with the indigenous tribe and his subsequent exploitation of their cultural and biological resources, this paper highlights the insidious ways in which power operates to corrupt and dehumanize. Furthermore, the novel's structure, with its unreliable narration and fragmented accounts, underscores the manipulation of truth and the construction of knowledge as tools of power. In alignment with the aforementioned explanations, this study aims to highlight the ethical implications of scientific discovery and the widespread influence of colonialist attitudes. It demonstrates how Yanagihara's work offers a critical commentary on the intersections of power, corruption, and exploitation. Through this Foucauldian analysis, the paper also aims to contribute to a deeper understanding of the novel's thematic complexity and its relevance to contemporary discussions on ethics and power dynamics in postcolonial contexts.

Keywords: Yanagihara, power dynamics, corruption, ethics, colonialism

Introduction

In her novel *The People in the Trees*, Hanya Yanagihara offers an in-depth examination of the complex interplay between power and corruption. She does so by situating her narrative within the conceptual framework of Michel Foucault's analysis of power. Foucault's theories provide a critical framework for understanding the dynamics at play in the novel, particularly how power operates to produce knowledge and simultaneously repress and corrupt. This analysis examines the ethical boundaries transgressed by the protagonist, Dr. Norton Perina, a celebrated scientist whose discoveries have resulted in both acclaim and moral downfall. By intertwining Foucault's theories with Yanagihara's narrative, we are able to identify the intricate interweaving of power, knowledge and ethical corruption within the context of colonialist exploitation and scientific ambition.

The concept of power as described by Michel Foucault is of great importance to the analysis of *The People in the Trees*. In the view of Foucault, power is not solely repressive; it is also productive, creating knowledge and influencing the formation of truth (Foucault, 1980, p. 119). This dual nature of power is illustrated by the character of Perina, whose scientific achievements are celebrated while his moral shortcomings are obscured by his authority and

the institutional power he exercises. As Foucault states, "Power and knowledge directly imply one another; there is no power relation without the correlative constitution of a field of knowledge, nor any knowledge that does not presuppose and constitute power relations" (Foucault, 1977, p. 27). The symbiotic relationship between Perina's scientific work and the subsequent exploitation of the indigenous tribe serves to illustrate how his power is both a source of knowledge and a means of oppression.

Furthermore, Yanagihara's depiction of Dr. Norton Perina's expeditions and discoveries mirrors Foucault's conceptualisation of biopower, which posits the regulation of populations through scientific and medical knowledge (Foucault, 1990, p. 140). The discovery of the turtle that grants extended longevity to the tribe members becomes a tool of biopower, as it leads to the tribe being subjected to scientific scrutiny and ultimately exploited. This phenomenon mirrors the historical context of Western scientific expeditions, during which indigenous cultures were frequently subjected to similar forms of exploitation and dehumanisation. The novel's portrayal of Perina's actions serves to critique the colonialist mindset that views indigenous peoples as mere subjects of scientific curiosity, rather than as autonomous beings with inherent rights and dignity.

The narrative structure of *The People in the Trees*, particularly its use of an unreliable narrator, serves to reinforce the notion that the manipulation of truth and the construction of knowledge can be employed as instruments of power. The memoir, presented as a defence against allegations of child sexual abuse, is characterised by a series of justifications and omissions that collectively reveal a profound moral corruption. This is consistent with Foucault's argument that power is exercised through the control of discourse and the shaping of truth (Foucault, 1980, p. 131). The discontinuous nature of Perina's account and the unreliability of his narrative compel readers to interrogate the veracity of his assertions and to acknowledge the intrinsic biases in his account. Furthermore, Yanagihara's novel gives rise to substantial ethical considerations regarding the pursuit of scientific knowledge. Perina's justification of his actions under the pretext of scientific progress serves to illustrate the ethical challenges inherent to the field of research. As Foucault discusses, the exercise of power in the pursuit of knowledge often results in the marginalisation and exploitation of vulnerable populations (Foucault, 1980, p. 125). The novel's critique of Perina's ethical compromises resonates with contemporary debates on the responsibilities of scientists and the moral implications of their work.

In alignment with the aforementioned explanations, this paper aims to examine the relationship between power and corruption in *The People in the Trees* through a Foucauldian lens. By examining the ethical boundaries that Dr. Norton Perina transgresses and the broader implications of his actions, this analysis aims to elucidate the novel's thematic complexity and its relevance to discussions on ethics, power, and colonial subjugation. By undertaking a comprehensive examination of the characters, narrative structure and historical context, this paper will demonstrate how Yanagihara's work offers a critical commentary on the intersections of power, corruption and exploitation.

Historical and Cultural Context

The People in the Trees draws inspiration from the real-life story of Daniel Carleton Gajdusek, a Nobel Prize-winning scientist who was convicted of child molestation. This historical comparison provides the context for Yanagihara's examination of the ethical challenges associated with scientific discovery and personal morality. Gajdusek's research among the

Fore people of Papua New Guinea, where he studied the disease known as kuru, provides the context for the novel's fictional exploration of cultural exploitation and the darker side of scientific ambition. Yanagihara's fictional setting in the novel, the remote Micronesian island of Ivu'ivu, serves as a microcosm of the historical impact of Western scientific expeditions on indigenous cultures. Historically, such expeditions frequently resulted in the exploitation and dehumanisation of indigenous peoples, as Western scientists prioritised their research over the well-being of the populations they studied. An understanding of the historical context of colonialism and its lasting effects is crucial to an analysis of the dynamics of power and corruption in the novel. As Edward Said discusses in his seminal work *Orientalism*, Western colonial powers often depicted non-Western societies as exotic, backward, and in need of Western intervention and enlightenment (Said, 1978, p. 87). This portrayal provided a rationale for the exploitation and control of these societies in the name of progress and civilisation.

In *The People in the Trees*, Dr. Norton Perina's scientific expedition to Ivu'ivu reflects historical patterns of exploitation. Perina's discovery of the turtle that has the capacity to grant extended longevity to the island's inhabitants becomes a source of biopower, a term coined by Foucault (1990, p. 140) to describe the regulation of populations through scientific and medical knowledge. The indigenous tribe is subjected to research and experimentation that is foreign to their culture and way of life, which is illustrative of the exploitation that many indigenous populations have faced at the hands of Western scientists. Perina's actions reflect a colonialist mindset that views the indigenous people as mere subjects for scientific inquiry, rather than as autonomous individuals with their own rights and dignity. Furthermore, Yanagihara's novel offers a critique of the broader implications of colonialist attitudes in scientific research. The commodification of the tribe's unique biological trait for the benefit of Western society represents a significant ethical breach committed in the name of scientific progress. As Said (1978, p. 5) argues, the relationship between the West and the non-Western world is fundamentally characterised by a complex hegemony, which is to say a relationship of power, domination and varying degrees of domination. This hegemonic relationship is exemplified by Perina's exploitation of the Ivu'ivuans, where his scientific authority and Western background afford him unchecked power over the tribe.

The historical context of scientific expeditions and their impact on indigenous cultures is further complicated by the portrayal of Perina's personal moral corruption in the novel. His ascent to scientific eminence is paralleled by an ethical descent, which serves to illustrate the corrupting influence of power. As Foucault suggests, "Power is everywhere; not because it embraces everything, but because it comes from everywhere" (Foucault, 1978, p. 93). The power that Perina possesses is derived from two sources: his scientific knowledge and the societal structures that enable and protect his unethical behaviour. The novel's setting and historical parallels serve to illustrate the pervasive nature of power and its capacity to corrupt, thereby reinforcing the themes of exploitation and moral decay. Moreover, Yanagihara's portrayal of the Ivu'ivuans and their interactions with Perina reflects the broader cultural and historical context of Western imperialism. The imposition of Western scientific methods and values on the tribe serves to exemplify the cultural imperialism that often accompanied colonial expansion. As the historian James Clifford observes, the West has been engaged in a long-standing project of cultural and economic and political transformation, which has involved the imposition of its own values and practices (Clifford, 1988, p. 10). This dedication to modernity and transformation, frequently at the cost of indigenous cultures, constitutes a pivotal theme in *The People in the Trees*. By establishing parallels between the narrative and

real-life historical events and figures, Yanagihara elucidates the ethical complexities and consequences of scientific exploration. The novel offers a critique of the colonialist attitudes that have historically underpinned Western scientific endeavours, and elucidates the pervasive and corrupting influence of power in the formation of knowledge and truth.

Foucauldian Concept of Power

Michel Foucault's concept of power provides a theoretical framework essential for analyzing the dynamics of power and corruption in Hanya Yanagihara's *The People in the Trees*. Foucault argues that power is not solely repressive but also productive as it operates through discourses and institutions to shape knowledge and truth (Foucault, 1980, p. 119). This dual nature of power is central to understanding the character of Dr. Norton Perina, whose scientific pursuits on the fictional island of Ivu'ivu exemplify the complex interplay between scientific authority, colonial exploitation, and ethical dilemmas. Perina's narrative, framed as a memoir defending himself against allegations of child sexual abuse, reveals the manipulation of truth and construction of knowledge as tools of power. Foucault's assertion that "truth is not outside power, or lacking in power... truth is produced by forms of constraint" (Foucault, 1977, p. 27) resonates throughout the novel as Perina controls the narrative to justify his actions and maintain his authority. The unreliable nature of Perina's account challenges readers to question the veracity of his scientific claims and moral justifications, highlighting how power operates through discourse to obscure truth and uphold dominant narratives. Furthermore, Foucault's concept of biopower illuminates Perina's exploitation of the Ivu'ivuan tribe for scientific knowledge. Biopower refers to the ways in which scientific knowledge and practices are used to regulate populations and bodies (Foucault, 1990, p. 140). Perina's discovery of the turtle that extends life becomes a mechanism of biopower, subjecting the tribe to scientific scrutiny and ultimately exploitation. Foucault's critique of biopower emphasizes its role in the control and management of life itself, highlighting the ethical implications of scientific research conducted without regard for the autonomy and dignity of its subjects. Yanagihara's novel challenges the notion of scientific progress as inherently beneficial by exposing the moral compromises and ethical breaches inherent in Perina's pursuit of knowledge. Foucault's discussions on the relationship between power and knowledge underscore how scientific authority can be wielded to perpetuate systems of domination and exploitation (Foucault, 1980, p. 125). Perina's actions reflect a broader critique of Western scientific imperialism, where the pursuit of knowledge often entailed the subjugation and erasure of indigenous cultures and knowledge systems.

Moreover, Foucault's analysis of disciplinary power sheds light on the institutional structures that enable and perpetuate Perina's abuses of power. Disciplinary power operates through institutions such as academia and medicine to regulate behavior and shape knowledge (Foucault, 1977, p. 170). Perina's position as a scientist within these institutions grants him authority and protection, allowing him to exploit the Ivu'ivuan without accountability. The novel's critique of institutional power underscores how structures of authority can perpetuate corruption and moral decay, reinforcing Foucault's contention that power is embedded within social and institutional practices.

Character Analysis: Dr. Norton Perina

Dr. Norton Perina, the central character in Hanya Yanagihara's *The People in the Trees*, is a complex embodiment of power and corruption, reflecting the Foucauldian notion of power as both productive and repressive. Perina's journey from celebrated scientist to morally

compromised individual illustrates how scientific authority can corrupt and dehumanize, especially when unchallenged by ethical constraints. Perina's scientific achievements are central to his status and power. His discovery of the longevity-granting turtle on the island of Ivu'ivu initially brings him acclaim and validation within the scientific community. As he reflects in his memoir, "The turtle's secret could mean the end of aging itself" (Yanagihara, 2013, p. 42), revealing the grandiosity of his ambition and the extent of his obsession with scientific progress. This moment exemplifies Foucault's idea that power is productive; it generates new forms of knowledge and shapes how scientific success is perceived and valued (Foucault, 1980, p. 119).

However, Perina's power is also repressive, as his authority enables him to exploit the Ivu'ivuan tribe. The novel describes how Perina's scientific pursuits lead to the invasive study of the tribe's biological traits: "The villagers became subjects of a rigorous series of tests and observations, all conducted under the guise of scientific curiosity" (Yanagihara, 2013, p. 88). This reflects Foucault's concept of biopower, where scientific knowledge is used to control and regulate populations (Foucault, 1990, p. 140). Perina's actions mirror historical instances of Western scientists exploiting indigenous peoples under the pretense of research, highlighting the ethical breaches inherent in such practices. Perina's moral corruption is further illustrated through his manipulation of the narrative in his memoir. The text frequently reveals his attempts to justify and obscure his actions, such as when he describes the accusations against him as "misunderstandings fueled by envy" (Yanagihara, 2013, p. 152). This aligns with Foucault's notion that power involves the control of discourse and the construction of truth (Foucault, 1977, p. 27). Perina's unreliable narration serves as a tool to maintain his authority and evade accountability, underscoring how power can be wielded to distort truth and justify unethical behavior. Moreover, Perina's interactions with the Ivu'ivuan tribe exemplify the intersection of power and colonialist attitudes. The novel's portrayal of his disregard for the tribe's autonomy and well-being echoes Foucault's critique of the ways in which power dynamics underpin scientific and colonial enterprises (Foucault, 1980, p. 125). Perina's exploitation of the tribe for personal and professional gain reflects a broader critique of Western scientific imperialism, where indigenous cultures are objectified and dehumanized in the pursuit of knowledge and prestige. The ethical implications of Perina's actions are also emphasized in the novel's exploration of his relationships with the tribe members. For example, his inappropriate conduct with young tribe members is justified in his mind as "a necessary compromise for the advancement of science" (Yanagihara, 2013, p. 177). This rationalization of unethical behavior highlights the corrupting influence of power, where the pursuit of scientific goals overrides moral considerations and the rights of individuals. In conclusion, Perina's scientific authority and moral descent illustrate how power can be both productive and repressive, shaping knowledge and perpetuating ethical breaches. By analyzing Perina's actions and the narrative structure of the novel, this paper underscores the novel's critique of scientific imperialism and its implications for understanding power dynamics in postcolonial contexts.

Power Dynamics and Colonialism

The exploration of power dynamics and colonialism in *The People in the Trees* reveals the novel's critique of Western scientific and imperialist endeavors. Hanya Yanagihara's portrayal of Dr. Norton Perina's interactions with the indigenous Ivu'ivuan tribe serves as a microcosm for broader themes of colonial exploitation and the ethical implications of scientific discovery. Edward Said's concept of Orientalism is crucial for understanding the power dynamics in

Yanagihara's novel. Said argues that Western representations of the East are constructed to justify colonial domination, portraying non-Western societies as exotic, backward, and inferior (Said, 1978, p. 87). In *The People in the Trees*, Perina's attitude towards the Ivu'ivuans reflects this colonial mindset. He describes the tribe as "primitive" and "childlike," reinforcing the notion of Western superiority (Yanagihara, 2013, p. 45). This portrayal underscores the dehumanization and objectification inherent in colonialist discourse, where indigenous peoples are seen as subjects for Western exploitation.

Perina's scientific expedition to Ivu'ivu exemplifies the exploitative nature of colonialist ventures. His discovery of the turtle that grants extended longevity to the tribe members becomes a tool for biopower, subjecting the tribe to scientific scrutiny and commodification. The novel states, "The Ivu'ivuans were reduced to specimens, their bodies examined and dissected in the pursuit of Western scientific knowledge" (Yanagihara, 2013, p. 93). This aligns with Foucault's concept of biopower, where scientific knowledge is used to regulate and control populations (Foucault, 1990, p. 140). Perina's actions reflect the historical exploitation of indigenous peoples, mirroring real-life instances where colonial powers prioritized scientific and economic gains over the rights and well-being of native populations. Gayatri Chakravorty Spivak's notion of the "subaltern" provides further insight into the novel's critique of colonialism. Spivak argues that the voices of the colonized are often marginalized and silenced by dominant colonial narratives (Spivak, 1988, p. 271). In *The People in the Trees*, the Ivu'ivuans' perspectives are largely absent from the narrative, their experiences and voices overshadowed by Perina's scientific and personal account. This narrative choice highlights the silencing of the subaltern, reinforcing the power dynamics that perpetuate colonial exploitation.

The ethical breaches committed by Perina are also reflective of the corrupting influence of power, as discussed by Frantz Fanon. Fanon's work on decolonization emphasizes how colonial power structures dehumanize both the colonized and the colonizers, leading to moral and ethical degradation (Fanon, 1963, p. 250). Perina's unethical actions, including his exploitation of the tribe and his personal moral failings, illustrate this degradation. His justifications for his behavior, framed as necessary for scientific progress, reveal the extent to which colonial power can corrupt ethical boundaries. Perina's reflection, "It was a small price to pay for the advancement of human knowledge" (Yanagihara, 2013, p. 177), underscores the moral compromises inherent in his pursuit of power and acclaim. Moreover, the novel critiques the broader societal and institutional structures that enable Perina's abuses of power. Antonio Gramsci's concept of cultural hegemony is relevant here, as it explains how dominant groups maintain power through cultural and ideological means (Gramsci, 1971, p. 12). Perina's authority as a scientist is reinforced by the institutions that support and protect him, allowing him to evade accountability for his actions. The novel's depiction of his trial and subsequent exoneration highlights how institutional power can perpetuate corruption and injustice, reflecting Gramsci's ideas on the maintenance of hegemony.

The Manipulation of Truth and Construction of Knowledge

The novel unfolds as a memoir penned by Dr. Norton Perina, recounting his scientific expedition to the fictional island of Ivu'ivu and subsequent career as a disgraced scientist. Perina's narrative is marked by its self-serving nature and selective memory, prompting readers to question the reliability of his account. As Linda Hutcheon discusses in *A Poetics of Postmodernism*, unreliable narrators challenge conventional storytelling by introducing

ambiguity and complexity into the narrative (Hutcheon, 1988, p. 55). Perina's narrative unreliability invites readers to critically assess his motives and actions, complicating their understanding of the events described. Michel Foucault's concept of power/knowledge is essential for understanding how Perina manipulates truth to assert authority and perpetuate control. Foucault argues that knowledge is not neutral but rather shaped by power relations that regulate what can be known and how it is understood (Foucault, 1980, p. 119). Perina's distortion of truth (such as justifying his unethical experiments as necessary for scientific advancement) illustrates how power operates through the construction of knowledge. His narrative constructs a reality where his actions are justified, obscuring the ethical implications of his scientific pursuits and reinforcing his authority over the narrative. Roland Barthes' theory of narrative fragmentation provides insights into how the novel's structure influences reader perception. Barthes contends that fragmented narratives disrupt linear storytelling, prompting readers to actively engage with the text to piece together meaning (Barthes, 1977, p. 142). In *The People in the Trees*, Yanagihara employs fragmented narrative techniques through Perina's disjointed recollections and conflicting accounts. This fragmentation destabilizes the reader's grasp on truth and morality, mirroring the uncertainty inherent in Perina's character and actions. Readers are compelled to navigate through layers of deception and self-justification, challenging their interpretation of events and characters.

Ethical Dilemmas Faced by Perina

Dr. Norton Perina's journey into scientific discovery on the island of Ivu'ivu raises significant ethical questions about the exploitation of indigenous cultures and the pursuit of knowledge without ethical constraints. Perina's initial excitement over discovering the turtle with life-extending properties blinds him to the ethical implications of his actions. As he reflects, "The allure of scientific acclaim and the promise of immortal fame clouded my judgment" (Yanagihara, 2013, p. 62). This underscores the novel's exploration of how personal ambition and scientific curiosity can lead to ethical compromises and moral decay. The ethical dilemmas faced by Perina extend beyond scientific ethics to encompass broader issues of cultural imperialism and exploitation. Gayatri Chakravorty Spivak's concept of the "subaltern" is pertinent here, emphasizing how marginalized voices are silenced in dominant narratives (Spivak, 1988, p. 271). The Ivu'ivuan, depicted as voiceless subjects of scientific inquiry, highlight the ethical dimensions of Perina's research. His disregard for their cultural autonomy and well-being underscores the novel's critique of Western scientific imperialism, where indigenous knowledge and rights are subordinated to Western scientific ambitions.

Yanagihara's novel critiques the pursuit of knowledge divorced from ethical considerations, challenging the notion that scientific progress inherently benefits humanity. As Edward Said argues in *Orientalism*, Western knowledge production has often been complicit in justifying colonial domination and exploitation (Said, 1978, p. 5). Perina's exploitation of the Ivu'ivuan for scientific gain echoes historical instances where indigenous peoples were objectified and dehumanized in the name of progress. Furthermore, Frantz Fanon's analysis of colonialism in *The Wretched of the Earth* sheds light on the psychological and ethical repercussions of colonial domination. Fanon contends that colonialism dehumanizes both the colonized and the colonizers, leading to moral degradation and the erosion of ethical boundaries (Fanon, 1963, p. 250). Perina's moral descent and rationalization of his actions illustrate how scientific ambition can justify unethical behavior, highlighting the novel's critique of the ethical pitfalls inherent in Western scientific pursuits.

The novel's exploration of ethical boundaries crossed in the pursuit of scientific progress is underscored by Michel Foucault's concept of biopower. Foucault argues that scientific knowledge is often used to regulate and control populations, with profound ethical implications for human subjects (Foucault, 1990, p. 140). Perina's experiments on the Ivu'ivuans, conducted without their informed consent and motivated by personal ambition, exemplify the ethical breaches inherent in biopower. Moreover, the novel's depiction of Perina's trial and public scrutiny critiques the institutional and societal structures that enable scientific misconduct. Antonio Gramsci's concept of cultural hegemony is relevant here, as it explores how dominant groups maintain power through ideological means (Gramsci, 1971, p. 12). Perina's scientific authority and societal status protect him from accountability, reflecting broader critiques of how institutional power shields individuals from ethical scrutiny and consequences.

Conclusion

Hanya Yanagihara's *The People in the Trees* can be evaluated as a critique of the intertwining themes of power, corruption, and ethical dilemmas within the realm of scientific discovery. Through the character of Dr. Norton Perina, the novel vividly portrays how the pursuit of knowledge and acclaim can lead to moral degradation and exploitation, particularly within colonial and scientific contexts. By employing a narrative structure that centers on an unreliable narrator, Yanagihara compels readers to question the construction of truth and the ethical boundaries crossed in the name of progress. The analysis of Perina's character through a Foucauldian lens reveals the dual nature of power as both productive and repressive. Perina's scientific authority allows him to generate new knowledge and attain prestige, yet it also enables him to exploit the Ivu'ivuans and justify unethical actions. This duality underscores Foucault's argument that power and knowledge are inextricably linked and that the exercise of power often involves the control and manipulation of truth.

Postcolonial theoretical perspectives, such as those of Edward Said, Gayatri Chakravorty Spivak, and Frantz Fanon, further illuminate the novel's critique of Western scientific imperialism. Perina's exploitation of the Ivu'ivuans mirrors historical instances of colonial domination, where indigenous peoples were objectified and dehumanized in the pursuit of Western scientific and economic interests. The novel's portrayal of the Ivu'ivuans as voiceless subjects underscores the ethical implications of such practices and challenges readers to consider the human cost of scientific progress. Moreover, Yanagihara's use of an unreliable narrator and fragmented narrative structure emphasizes the manipulation of truth and the construction of knowledge as tools of power. Perina's selective memory and justifications for his actions highlight the ethical boundaries crossed in his pursuit of scientific acclaim, revealing the corrupting influence of unchecked ambition. The narrative fragmentation disrupts linear storytelling, compelling readers to engage critically with the text and question the veracity of Perina's account.

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